

Questionnaire on the noncausal-causal alternation (based on Haspelmath 1993:97)

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ENGLISH	KISWAHILI
<p>Instructions</p> <p>This questionnaire consists of English and Swahili sentences. For each English/Swahili sentence, we would like you to provide a similar sentence in your language that conveys the same message.</p> <p>Here is an example of what the questionnaire looks like. Each sentence is preceded by a context to explain in which situation the sentence could be used. The context has a grey background. The blank space in the last line is for the sentence in your language. You do not have to translate the context.</p>	<p>Maelekezo</p> <p>Hojaji hii ina sentensi za Kiingereza na Kiswahili. Kwenye kila sentensi, tungependa utoe sentensi kutoka kwenye lugha yako ambayo inalingana na sentensi ya Kiingereza/Kiswahili iliyotolewa.</p> <p>Sentensi ifuatayo imetolewa kama mfano kuonyesha namna ya kujaza hojaji hii. Kila sentensi iliyotolewa imetanguliwa na muktadha unaoonyesha mazingira ambayo hiyo sentensi inaweza kutumika. Muktadha umewekewa kivuli cha rangi ya kijivu. Nafasi iliyoachwa wazi kwenye mstari wa mwisho itumie kuandika tafsiri ya sentensi ya Kiingereza/Kiswahili kwenye lugha yako. Usitafsiri muktadha wa matumizi ya sentensi zilizotolewa.</p>

WAKE UP (SPONTANEOUSLY, BY ONESELF) / WAKE SOMEONE UP

	Context
EN	<i>Komba's alarm went off early in the morning while he was sleeping.</i>
SW	<i>Alamu ya Komba ililia asubuhi na mapema wakati Komba alipokuwa amelala.</i>
1.	Sentence
EN	Komba woke up early.
SW	Komba aliamka mapema.
TL	

This questionnaire is about verbs and the words surrounding verbs. You will see that there are several sentences with the same verb, but the number and/or order of the words surrounding the verb are different.

Hojaji hii inahusu vitenzi na maneno yanayovizunguka. Utagundua kwamba kuna sentensi kadhaa zilizoundwa na kitenzi kimoja, ambapo namba na/au mfuatano wa maneno unaovizunguka vitenzi uko tofauti.

The questionnaire starts on the next page.

Hojaji yenyewe inaanza ukurasa unaofuata.

EN: Questionnaire

SW: Hojaji

WAKE UP (SPONTANEOUSLY, BY ONESELF) / WAKE SOMEONE UP

	Context
EN	<i>Early in the morning a storm was raging outside while Komba was sleeping.</i>
SW	<i>Leo asubuhi kulikuwa na ngurumo na radi wakati komba alipokuwa amelala.</i>
1.	Sentence
EN	Komba woke up early.
SW	Komba aliamka mapema.
TL	
2.	Sentence
EN	Komba woke up early from the thunder.
SW	Komba aliamshwa mapema na ladi.
TL	
	Context
EN	<i>Komba's father was sleeping. Someone called on the phone to talk to Komba's father.</i>
SW	<i>Baba yake Komba alikuwa amelala. Mtu akapiga simu akitaka kuongea na baba yake Komba.</i>
3.	Sentence
EN	Komba woke up his father.
SW	Komba alimwamsha baba yake.
TL	

BREAK;BE BROKEN / BREAK SOMETHING

	Context
EN	<i>You enter a room and are looking for your favorite cup to drink, but it is in pieces on the floor.</i>
SW	<i>Unaingia chumbani na unatafuta kikombe chako ukipendacho unywe (maji), lakini unakikuta kikombe kipo kwenye vipandevipande sakafuni.</i>
4.	Sentence
EN	The cup is broken.
SW	Kikombe kimevunjika.
TL	
	Context
EN	<i>There was an earthquake earlier today. Afterwards you looked for your favorite cup and you find it in pieces on the floor.</i>
SW	<i>Leo mapema kulikuwa na tetemeko la ardhi. Baadaye ulitafuta kikombe chako unachokipenda na ukakikuta vipandevipande sakafuni.</i>
5.	Sentence
EN	The cup is broken because of/by the earthquake.
SW	Kikombe kimevunjika kwa sababu ya tetemeko la ardhi.
TL	
	Context
EN	<i>Somebody tells you the cup was broken because Komba dropped it.</i>
SW	<i>Kuna mtu alikuambia kikombe kilivunjika kwa sababu komba alikidondosha.</i>
6.	Sentence
EN	The cup was broken by Komba.
SW	Kikombe kilivunjwa na Komba.
TL	
	Context
EN	<i>You enter a room and are looking for your favorite cup to drink, but it is in pieces on the</i>

	SW	<i>floor. You ask who broke it.</i> <i>Unaingia chumbani na unatafuta kikombe chako ukipendacho unywe (maji), lakini unakikuta kikombe kipo kwenye vipandevipande sakafuni. Unauliza nani alikivunja.</i>
7.	EN	Sentence Komba broke the cup.
	SW	Komba alikivunja kikombe.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>Komba had a car accident and his arm hurts. He goes to the doctor to have it checked. The doctor doesn't have good news.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba alipata ajali ya gari na kuumia mkono. Anaenda kwa daktari kwa ajili ya uchunguzi. Daktari anampa habari mbaya.</i>
8.	EN	Sentence Komba's arm is broken.
	SW	Mkono wa Komba umevunjika.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>You tell a friend about the accident that Komba was in and what happened to his arm.</i>
	SW	<i>Unamweleza rafiki yako juu ya ajali ya Komba na kilichotokea kwenye mkono wake.</i>
9.	EN	Sentence Komba broke his arm.
	SW	Komba alivunja mkono wake.
	TL	
10.	EN	Sentence Komba broke his arm in an accident.
	SW	Komba alivunja mkono wake kwenye ajali.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>Komba is feeling a lot of pain in his injured arm.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba anahisi maumivu makali kwenye mkono wake ulioumia/alioumia.</i>
11.	EN	Sentence Komba's broken arm hurts.
	SW	Mkono wa Komba uliovunjika unauma.
	TL	

BURN / BURN SOMETHING

	EN	Context <i>Komba has made a fire with some wood.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba amewasha moto kwa kuni.</i>
12.	EN	Sentence The wood is burning.
	SW	Kuni zinaungua.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>Komba puts a lit match into a pile of wood.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba anawasha kiberiti kwenye lundo la kuni.</i>
13.	EN	Sentence Komba is burning the wood.
	SW	Komba anaunguza kuni.
	TL	

14.	EN	Context <i>Komba's house caught fire from a bushfire.</i>
	SW	<i>Moto wa mstituni umeunguza nyumba ya Komba.</i>
14.	EN	Sentence Komba's house is burning because of/due to the bushfire.
	SW	Nyumba ya komba inaungua kutokana na moto wa msituni.
	TL	

DIE / KILL

15.	EN	Context <i>Komba was suffering from malaria.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba aliugua malaria/Komba alikuwa anaumwa malaria.</i>
15.	EN	Sentence Komba died today.
	SW	Komba amekufa leo.
	TL	
16.	EN	Sentence Komba died today from malaria.
	SW	Komba amekufa leo kwa malaria.
	TL	
17.	EN	Context <i>Komba was working on the farm with his machete, when he saw a dangerous snake.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba alikuwa na jambia shambani wakati alipomwona nyoka wa hatari.</i>
17.	EN	Sentence Komba killed the snake.
	SW	Komba alimua nyoka.
	TL	
18.	EN	Sentence Komba killed the snake with his machete.
	SW	Komba alimua nyoka kwa jambia.
	TL	

OPEN;BE OPEN / OPEN SOMETHING

19.	EN	Context <i>There are a couple of bags of rice in a shop. Komba wants to take an amount of rice from a sack and is looking for one that is open. The seller shows him an open sack and says:</i>
	SW	<i>Dukani kuna magunia mengi ya mchele. Komba anataka kuchukua kiasi cha mchele kwenye gunia na anatafuta moja lililofunguliwa. Muuzaji anamuonesha gunia lililofunguliwa na kusema:</i>
19.	EN	Sentence That bag of rice is open.
	SW	Gunia hilo la mchele limefunguka.
	TL	

20.	Context	EN Komba wanted to cook dinner with some rice. He bought a new bag of rice that is not open. SW Komba alitaka kupika wali kama chakula cha jioni. Alinunua gunia jipya la mchele ambalo halijafunguliwa.
	Sentence	EN Komba opened a bag of rice. SW Komba alifungua gunia la mchele. TL
21.	Context	EN Komba was sitting in his living room, when he felt a strong wind blowing from outside. He saw that the door was open. SW Komba alikuwa amekaa sebuleni kwake, alipohisi upepo mkali umavuma kutoka nje. Alibaini kuwa mlango ulikuwa wazi.
	Sentence	EN The door was opened by/because of the wind. SW Mlango ulifunguka na upepo. TL

CLOSE; BE CLOSED / CLOSE SOMETHING

22.	Context	EN You ask Komba if he bought maize today. You forgot it is a holiday and shops are not open. Komba replies with the following sentence. SW Unamuuliza Komba kama leo alinunua mahindi. Ulisahau kuwa leo ni wikendi na maduka yamefungwa.
	Sentence	EN The shops are closed today. SW Leo maduka yamefungwa. TL
23.	Context	EN Komba owns a shop which is always open in the evening. However, yesterday Komba became sick in the afternoon and had to go home. SW Komba anamiliki duka ambalo huwa wazi kila siku jioni. Hata hivyo, jana Komba aliugua mchana hivyo akaenda nyumbani.
	Sentence	EN Komba closed his shop yesterday. SW Komba alifunga duka lake jana. TL

BEGIN / BEGIN SOMETHING

	Context	
	EN	<i>Komba plays football and practises with his team on Sunday afternoon. He usually meets with a friend before training in the morning. However, the previous weekend training was moved to the morning. Komba forgot to tell his friend they couldn't meet. When his friend calls him to ask why Komba didn't show up, Komba replies:</i>
	SW	<i>Komba hucheza mpira wa miguu na hufanya mazoezi na timu yake kila jumapili mchana. Hukutana na marafiki asubuhi kabla ya mazoezi. Hata hivyo, wikendi iliyopita mazoezi yalipangwa asubuhi. Komba alisahau kuwajulisha rafiki zake kuwa wasingekutana. Marafiki walipompigia kumuuliza kwa nini hakuonekana, Komba alijibu:</i>
24.	Sentence	
	EN	The practice began in the morning.
	SW	Mazoezi yalianza asubuhi.
	TL	
25.	Sentence	
	EN	My team began practice in the morning.
	SW	Timu yangu ilianza mazoezi asubuhi.
	TL	

LEARN / TEACH

	Context	
	EN	<i>Komba's child is just starting to speak. At home, Komba is speaking Swahili to his child.</i>
	SW	<i>Mtoto wa Komba ameanza kuongea. Komba humwongelesha Kiswahili mtoto wake akiwa nyumbani.</i>
26.	Sentence	
	EN	Komba's child is learning Swahili.
	SW	Moto wa Komba anajifunza Kiswahili.
	TL	
27.	Sentence	
	EN	Komba is teaching his child.
	SW	Komba anamfundisha mtoto wake.
	TL	
28.	Sentence	
	EN	Komba is teaching his child Swahili.
	SW	Komba anamfundisha mtoto wake Kiswahili.
	TL	

GATHER / GATHER PEOPLE OR SOMETHING

	Context	
	EN	<i>The principal wanted to discuss something with the teachers.</i>
	SW	<i>Mkuu wa Chuo alitaka kujadili jambo na walimu.</i>
29.	Sentence	
	EN	The teachers gathered (in school for a meeting).
	SW	Walimu walikusanyika (shuleni kwa ajili ya mkutano).
	TL	

30.	Sentence	EN SW TL	The principle gathered the teachers (in school for a meeting). Mkuu wa Chuo aliwakusanya walimu (shuleni kwa ajili ya mkutano).
	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba is cleaning his house. In one room, there is a lot of dust in one corner.</i> <i>Komba anasafisha nyumba yake. Katika chumba kimoja, kuna uchafu mwingi kwenye kona.</i>
31.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Dust has gathered in the corner. Uchafu umejikusanya/umekusanyika kwenye kona.
	Context	EN SW	<i>While Komba was cleaning his house, he swept the floor that was covered with dust.</i> <i>Wakati Komba anafanya usafi nyumbani kwake, alifagia sakafu iliyokuwa imejaa uchafu.</i>
32.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba has gathered dust in the corner. Komba amekusanya uchafu kwenye kona.

SPREAD / SPREAD SOMETHING

33.	Context	EN SW	<i>Somebody asks when malaria spread in Tanzania.</i> <i>Mtu anataka kujua ni lini malaria ilienea Tanzania.</i>
	Sentence	EN SW TL	Malaria spread a long time ago. Malaria ilienea miaka mingi iliyopita.
34.	Context	EN SW	<i>Somebody asks how malaria spread in Tanzania.</i> <i>Mtu anauliza namna ambavyo malaria ilienea Tanzania.</i>
	Sentence	EN SW TL	Mosquitos spread malaria a long time ago. Mbu walieneza Malaria siku nyingi zilizopita.
35.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Malaria was spread by mosquitos. Malaria ilienezwa na mbu.

SINK / SINK SOMETHING

36.	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba's neighbor wants to go fishing on the lake, and always uses Komba's canoe. He comes to Komba's house for the canoe, but the canoe isn't there. Komba explains to his neighbor what happened.</i> <i>Jirani yake Komba hupenda kuvua ziwani, na kila wakati anatumia mtumbwi wa Komba. Anafika nyumbani kwa Komba kuazima mtumbwi lakini haukuti. Komba anamfafanulia kilichotokea.</i>
	Sentence	EN	The canoe sunk (in the lake).

	SW TL	Mtumbwi ulizama (ziwani).
	EN SW	Context <i>Komba's neighbor goes back home and explains to his wife why he has not gone fishing. Jirani yake Komba alirejea nyumbani na kumweleza mke wake kwa nini hakwenda kuvua samaki.</i>
37.	EN SW TL	Sentence Komba sunk his canoe (in the lake). Komba alizamisha mtumbwi wake (ziwani).

CHANGE / CHANGE SOMETHING

	EN SW	Context <i>Komba's house used to be bright yellow. After many years the color has faded. His friend, who hasn't visited Komba for many years, passes Komba's house. He talks to his wife about the color.</i> <i>Nyumba ya Komba ilikuwa na rangi ya njano iliyong'aa. Baada ya miaka mingi rangi ilififia. Rafiki yake ambaye hakumtembelea Komba kwa miaka mingi, anapita nje ya nyumba hiyo. Anazungumza na mke wake kuhusu rangi hiyo.</i>
38.	EN SW TL	Sentence The color of Komba's house changed. Rangi ya Nyumba ya Komba imebadilika.
	EN SW	Context <i>Komba's house used to be yellow. In the previous week he painted his house green. When his friend passes by Komba's house, he talks to his wife about the color.</i> <i>Rangi ya Nyumba ya Komba ilikuwa njano. Wiki iliyopita alipaka rangi ya kijani. Wakati rafiki yake alipita karibu na nyumba hiyo, anaongea na mke wake kuhusu rangi hiyo.</i>
39.	EN SW TL	Sentence Komba changed the color of his house. Komba alibadilisha rangi ya nyumba yake.

DISSOLVE / DISSOLVE SOMETHING

	EN SW	Context <i>Komba's wife is sick, and she needs to drink water with a powder. Komba prepares the drink by putting the powder in the water.</i> <i>Mke wa Komba ni Mgonjwa, na anahitaji kunywa dawa na maji. Komba anaandaa maji na kuyawekea dawa.</i>
40.	EN SW TL	Sentence The powder dissolves in the water. Dawa inachanganyika kwenye maji.
41.	EN SW TL	Sentence Komba dissolves the powder in the water. Komba anachanganya dawa kwenye maji.

DESTROY;BE DESTROYED / DESTROY SOMETHING

	EN	Context <i>There was a big storm with heavy rainfall.</i>
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42.	SW	<i>Kulikuwa na kimbunga kikali chenye mvua kubwa.</i>
	EN	Sentence Komba's house was destroyed.
	SW	Nyumba ya Komba iliharibika.
	TL	
43.	EN	Sentence Komba's house was destroyed by the rain.
	SW	Nyumba ya Komba iliharibika na mvua.
	TL	
44.	EN	Sentence The rain destroyed Komba's house.
	SW	Mvua iliharibu nyumba ya Komba.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>Komba comes home from work and finds his television completely broken on the floor.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba anarejea nyumbani kutoka kazini anakuta runinga yake imevunjika kabisa sakafuni.</i>
45.	EN	Sentence The television is destroyed.
	SW	Runinga imeharibika.
	TL	
46.	EN	Sentence The television was destroyed by his child.
	SW	Runinga iliharibiwa na mtoto wake.
	TL	
47.	EN	Sentence His child destroyed the television.
	SW	Mtoto wake aliharibu runinga.
	TL	

BECOME LOST / LOSE

	EN	Context <i>Komba wants to call his wife but he can't find his phone.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba anataka kumpigia mke wake lakini haioni simu yake.</i>
48.	EN	Sentence Komba's phone is lost.
	SW	Simu ya Komba imepotea.
	TL	
49.	EN	Sentence Komba lost his phone.
	SW	Komba alipoteza simu yake.
	TL	

DRY / DRY SOMETHING

	EN	Context <i>Komba washed his clothes and hung them on a line outside.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba alifua nguo zake na kuzianika nje kwenye kamba.</i>
50.	EN	Sentence His clothes are drying (in the sun).
	SW	Nguo zake zinakauka (juani).

51.	TL	
	EN	Sentence Komba is drying his clothes (in the sun).
	SW	Komba anaanika nguo zake (juani).
	TL	

CONNECT;BE CONNECTED / CONNECT SOMETHING

	ENG	Context <i>Two villages were separated by a river for a long time, until the people built a bridge.</i>
	SW	<i>Vijiji viwili vilikuwa vimetenganishwa na mto kwa muda mrefu. Ilifikia wakati watu wakajenga daraja.</i>
52.	EN	Sentence Now, the two villages are connected.
	SW	Kwa sasa, vijiji vimeunganishwa/vimeungana.
	TL	
53.	EN	Sentence The two villages are connected by the bridge.
	SW	Vijiji viwili vimeunganishwa na daraja.
	TL	
54.	EN	Sentence The bridge connects the two villages.
	SW	Daraja limeunganisha vijiji viwili.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>Komba broke his arm in an accident. After three months his arm is healed.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba alivunja mkono wake kwenye ajali. Baada ya miwezi mitatu mkono wake ulipona.</i>
55.	EN	Sentence The bones of the broken arm are connected.
	SW	Mkono uliovunjika imeunga.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>Komba broke his arm in an accident. He goes to see a doctor to treat his arm.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba alivunja mkono wake kwenye ajali. Alienda hospitali kumwona daktari kwa ajili ya matibabu.</i>
56.	EN	Sentence The doctor connected the bones of the broken arm.
	SW	Dakatari aliunganisha mifupa ya mkono uliovunjika.
	TL	

BOIL / BOIL SOMETHING

	EN	Context <i>Komba is heating water in order to cook rice. After a while, the water starts to boil.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba anachemsha maji ili apike wali. Baada ya muda mfupi maji yanaaza kuchemka.</i>
57.	EN	Sentence The water is boiling.
	SW	Maji yamechemka.
	TL	
58.	EN	Sentence Komba is boiling water.

SW	Komba amechemsha maji.
TL	

ROCK / ROCK SOMETHING ≈ SWING / SWING SOMETHING ≈ SWAY / SWAY SOMETHING

59.	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba's child is sitting on a swing, pushing herself back and forth.</i> <i>Mtoto wa Komba amekaa kwenye bembea, akijisukuma mweneyewe kwenda nyuma na mbele.</i>
	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba's child is swinging (on the swing.) Mtoto wa Komba anabembea (kwenye bembea).
60.	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba is playing with his child. His child is sitting in a swing and Komba is pushing his child in the swing.</i> <i>Komba anacheza na mtoto wake. Mtoto wake amekaa kwenye bembea na Komba anamsukuma.</i>
	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba is swinging his child. Komba anambembeza mtoto wake.
61.	Context	EN SW	<i>There is a strong wind blowing.</i> <i>Kuna upepo mkali unavuma.</i>
	Sentence	EN SW TL	The trees are swaying. Miti inayumba.
62.	Sentence	EN SW TL	The trees are swaying because of the wind. Miti inayumba na upepo.
63.	Sentence	EN SW TL	The wind is swaying the trees. Upepo unayumbisha miti.

GO OUT / PUT OUT

64.	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba made a small fire in the evening outside his house. He left the fire and went inside to sleep.</i> <i>Komba aliwasha moto mdogo nje ya nyumba yake. Aliacha moto na kwenda ndani kulala.</i>
	Sentence	EN SW TL	The fire went out during/in the night. Moto ulizim(ik)a wakati wa usiku.
	Context	EN	<i>Komba made a small fire in the evening outside his house. Before he went inside, he extinguished the fire.</i>

	SW	<i>Komba aliwasha moto mdogo wakati wa jioni nje ya nyumba yake. Kabla ya kuingia ndani aliuzima.</i>
65.	EN	Sentence Komba put out the fire.
	SW	Komba alizima moto.
	TL	
66.	EN	Sentence Komba put out the fire with water.
	SW	Komba alizima moto kwa maji.
	TL	

RISE / RAISE

	EN	Context <i>Komba is a teacher in primary school. Last year, he did certain activities to upgrade his salary.</i>
	SW	<i>Komba ni mwalimu wa shule ya msingi. Mwaka jana alijiendeleza ili kuongeza mshahara wake.</i>
67.	EN	Sentence Last year, Komba's salary rose from grade A to B.
	SW	Mwaka jana mshahara wa Komba ulipanda kutoka daraja A kwenda B.
	TL	
	EN	Context <i>On Labour Day last year, the president announced that teachers will get a raise.</i>
	SW	<i>Kwenye siku ya wafanyakazi mwaka jana, rais alitangaza kwamba walimu watapata nyongeza ya mshahara.</i>
68.	EN	Sentence Last year, the president raised the teachers' salary.
	SW	Mwaka jana rais alipandisha mishahara ya walimu.
	TL	

FINISH; BE FINISHED / FINISH SOMETHING

	EN	Context <i>Komba works on his farm today. He has to water the plants. At the end of the day he has watered them all.</i>
	SW	<i>Leo Komba anafanya kazi shambani kwake. Anapaswa kumwagilia mimea. Jioni ilipofika alikuwa amemwagilia mimea yote.</i>
69.	EN	Sentence Komba's work is finished.
	SW	Kazi ya Komba imekamilika.
	TL	
70.	EN	Sentence Komba finished his work.
	SW	Komba alikamilisha kazi yake.
	TL	

TURN AROUND / TURN SOMEONE OR SOMETHING AROUND

	EN	Context <i>Komba's child is running around in front of the house, when Komba called her to come inside.</i>
	SW	<i>Mtoto wa Komba alikuwa anakimbia kuzunguka mbele ya nyumba, wakati Komba alipomwita aingie ndani.</i>

71.	Sentence
	EN The child turned around.
	SW TL Mtoto aligeuka nyuma.
72.	Context
	EN <i>Komba's child is sitting on the floor facing the television. Komba wants to talk to her, so he picks her up to face the couch.</i>
	SW TL <i>Mtoto wa Komba amekaa sakafuni kutazamana runinga. Komba anataka kuzungumza naye, kwa hiyo anamnyanyua ili kutazama kochi.</i>
72.	Sentence
	EN Komba turned around his child.
	SW TL Komba alimgeuza mtoto wake.

ROLL / ROLL SOMETHING

73.	Context
	EN <i>There is a football field on the top of a hill. During a game, someone kicked the ball towards the hillside.</i>
	SW TL <i>Kuna uwanja wa mpira wa miguu kwenye kilele cha kilima. Wakati wa mchezo, mtu akaupiga mpira ukaangukia bondeni.</i>
73.	Sentence
	EN The ball rolled down the hill.
	SW TL Mpira uliviringika kutoka kwenye mlima.
74.	Context
	EN <i>Komba stood on top of the hillside and kicked the ball over the edge.</i>
	SW TL <i>Komba alisimama juu ya kilele cha mlima na kupiga mpira kuelekea pembezoni.</i>
74.	Sentence
	EN Komba rolled the ball down the hill.
	SW TL Komba aliviringishia mpira kutoka mlimani.

COOL DOWN / COOL SOMETHING DOWN ≈ FREEZE / FREEZE SOMETHING

75.	Context
	EN <i>Komba has boiled water and made tea. He was called away and forgot about it.</i>
	SW TL <i>Komba amechemsha maji na kutengeneza chai. Kuna mtu alimuita akasahau chai.</i>
75.	Sentence
	EN The tea is cooling down.
	SW TL Chai inapoa.
76.	Context
	EN <i>Komba is drinking hot tea. Before he puts it in his mouth, he blows the tea.</i>
	SW TL <i>Komba anakunywa chai ya moto. Kabla hajaiweka mdomoni, anaipuliza.</i>
76.	Sentence
	EN Komba is cooling down the tea.
	SW TL Komba anapoza chai.

MELT / MELT SOMETHING

	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba cooked something with butter. He put the butter in a pan on the fire.</i> <i>Komba alipika [chakula] kwa kutumia siagi (au blueband). Aliweka siagi kwenye kikaango kilichokuwa jikoni.</i>
77.	Sentence	EN SW TL	The butter melted. Siagi iliyeyuka.
78.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba melted the butter. Komba aliyeyusha siagi.

FILL / FILL SOMETHING

	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba left a pot outside. During the night it rained, and rain fell into the pot.</i> <i>Komba aliacha chungu nje. Usiku mvua ilinyesha na maji yakaingia kwenye chungu.</i>
79.	Sentence	EN SW TL	The pot filled with water. Chungu kilijaa maji.
	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba cooked rice yesterday.</i> <i>Jana Komba alipika wali.</i>
80.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba filled the pot with water. Komba alijaza maji kwenye chungu.

IMPROVE / IMPROVE SOMETHING

	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba was very ill for a long time, but now he is slowly getting better.</i> <i>Komba alikuwa mgonjwa sana kwa muda mrefu, lakini kwa sasa taratibu anapata nafuu.</i>
81.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba's health improved. Afya ya Komba inaimarika.
	Context	EN SW	<i>Komba was a very lazy person, eating bad foods and not exercising. Because of this, he was not healthy. But now Komba is eating better and doing a lot of exercises to restore his health.</i> <i>Komba alikuwa mtu mvivu sana, anakula chakula kibaya na hafanyi mazoezi. Kwa sababu hiyo, hakuwa na afya nzuri. Lakini kwa sasa Komba anakula vizuri na kufanya sana mazoezi ili kuimarisha afya yake.</i>
82.	Sentence	EN SW TL	Komba is improving his health. Komba anaimarisha afya yake.

DEVELOP / DEVELOP SOMETHING ≈ GROW / GROW SOMETHING

	Context
EN	<i>Komba is building a house, and he works hard on it every day.</i>
SW	<i>Komba anajenga nyumba, na anajenga kwa bidii kila siku.</i>
83.	Sentence
EN	The building is developing.
SW	Jengo linaendelea.
TL	
84.	Sentence
EN	Komba is developing the building.
SW	Komba anaendeleza jengo (lake).
TL	

SPLIT / SPLIT SOMETHING [≈ BURST / BURST SOMETHING]

	Context
EN	<i>Komba has a baobab fruit. He dropped it on the floor.</i>
SW	<i>Komba alikuwa na ubuyu. Akaudondosha sakafuni.</i>
85.	Sentence
EN	The baobab fruit split.
SW	Ubuyu ukapasuka.
TL	
	Context
EN	<i>Komba has a baobab fruit.</i>
SW	<i>Komba ana ubuyu.</i>
86.	Sentence
EN	Komba split the baobab fruit.
SW	Komba alipasua ubuyu.
TL	
	Context
EN	<i>There's an island in the middle of a big river.</i>
SW	<i>Kuna kisiwa katikati ya mto mkubwa.</i>
87.	Sentence
EN	The river is split by the island.
SW	Mto umegawanywa na kisiwa.
TL	
88.	Sentence
EN	The island splits the river.
SW	Kisiwa kimeugawa mto.
TL	

STOP / STOP SOMETHING

	Context
EN	<i>Komba parked his car near the river but forgot to use the break. The car started the roll towards the river. Fortunately, it did not roll into the river.</i>
SW	<i>Komba aliegasha gari yake karibu na mto lakini alisahau kuweka breki. Gari lilianza kuserereka kuelekea mtoni. Kwa bahati nzuri halikuangukia mtoni.</i>
89.	Sentence
EN	The car stopped in front of the river.
SW	Gari lilisimama mbele ya mto.
TL	

90.	EN SW	Context <i>Komba was driving with his family to a place near the river. They found a good spot.</i> <i>Komba alikuwa anaendesha gari akiwa na familia yake katika eneo lilokuwa karibu na mto. Wakaona eneo zuri.</i>
	EN SW TL	Sentence Komba stopped the car. Komba alisimamisha gari.